

Questionnaire to be responded by the Participants

4 respostas

Profile of Participants (reusing question 4 of the " Beyond Code Generation: An Observational Study of ChatGPT Usage in Software Engineering Practice" Exit Survey)

What is your level of experience in ChatGPT?

 Copiar

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What is your level of expertise in the NFR Framework?

 Copiar

4 respostas

What is your level of expertise in Transparency?

4 respostas

Quantitative Evaluation (reusing questions 5, 7, 8, 13, and 14 from "Beyond Code Generation: An Observational Study of ChatGPT Usage in Software Engineering Practice" Exit Survey)

Did ChatGPT provide helpful responses to your questioning?

4 respostas

How did you perceive ChatGPT level of understandability for your questioning?

4 respostas

What is the level of Trust you would assign to ChatGPT based on its answers to questioning?

4 respostas

How helpful was the interaction with ChatGPT?

 Copiar

4 respostas

After using ChatGPT for this research, what are the potential you see in using it for further research?

 Copiar

4 respostas

Qualitative Evaluation (inspired by questions 10 and 11 from "Beyond Code Generation: An Observational Study of ChatGPT Usage in Software Engineering Practice" Exit Survey)

Write a summary of your experience focusing on consistency and on what you have learned

4 respostas

Considering the overall experience, ChatGPT provided useful responses regarding transparency, soft goals, and correlations. Its answers were clear and explanatory, which can be especially helpful for those unfamiliar with the concept of transparency. Most of the time, the responses appropriately considered the context provided, although there were some inconsistencies concerning the level of granularity of the requirements, as well as in contributions and correlations.

Despite the positive experience, there are some points worth noting:

Some questions had to be asked multiple times in different ways because the answers were incomplete, failing to address parts of the question or context.

The responses tend to follow a standard medium length, regardless of the complexity of the question or answer, often resulting in shallow and generic responses.

The responses often agree with the question, displaying a complacent attitude toward the presented information. For this reason, the strategy involved identifying what was missing or incorrect.

Providing too much context tends to bias the answers. In the future, a complementary strategy could involve requesting more than one alternative response or asking for different points of view.

There were some inconsistencies in the given answers.

On the other hand, these negative points (except for the second) are commonly encountered when conducting interviews with people as well, highlighting the need to consider various individuals, viewpoints, and strategies. In other words, using ChatGPT doesn't exempt us from these precautions and may even require additional considerations. However, on a positive note, it has a low cost, can speed up exploratory phases, and makes complex knowledge more accessible.

Como disse no artigo, eu entendi que o ChatGPT respondeu sem fazer uma análise semântica das suas respostas. Ou seja ele não levou em consideração, por exemplo que acessibilidade em relação a transparência é fundamentalmente uma questão de acesso ao objeto da transparência, isto é o [tópico] para qual se aplica a qualidade. A questão de facilidade de uso (usabilidade) é outra coisa. No entanto, nas fontes de informação que usou, o termo acessibilidade é utilizado desde da perspectiva de quem usa e não da disponibilidade do objeto. O termo acessibilidade é comumente utilizado na perspectiva do usuário, ou seja está conectada ao fundamental aspecto de tornar o objeto de fácil uso independente das características do usuário.

ChatGPT may show distinct answers if you ask the same question at different moments. The chat history may also lead to other answers.

So, ChatGPT does not have "knowledge" from a body of information because this software lacks consistency in its affirmations. It will say "sorry" or "you are right" when asked, "Are you sure?"

It is not a reliable source of information. But it helps a lot in different ways.

In general it is coherent since all the answers are justified. However, when I tried to fit the qualities into the TSIG, I realized that many concepts already encompass what was suggested. On the other hand, ChatGPT suggested other groups of qualities, which make sense but from a point of view X that is different from the one from which the TSIG was carried out. In that sense, I think that my prompt strategy may not have been the best by asking about each group of qualities without giving the context of the entire TSIG graph and also the sources used for that.

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